

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Blendtec is known for their specialty in the sale of household and industrial blenders. It is a subsidiary of K-TEC Inc and the founder is Tom Dickson who founded it in 1975 with its location still at Orem, Utah till date, 2020 with over 500 employees.

Tom Dickson, the founder of blendtec invented a wheat mill that changed the face of home milling industry, he made sales of over 40,000 mills in few years. He continued with all kinds of innovation which included a multi-function machine that produced 12 pounds of bread dough and included a blender used by so many restaurants, this led to his developing an industrial blender found in places like Starbucks, Jamba juice, Ben and Jerry's and Baskin-Robbins etc.

The blender is proudly made in America and it's a family owned business. Blendtec's commitment is "We believe in our products so you can too" Durable and safe with its blades blunt not sharp and spins at over 200 miles per hour and can crush almost everything. It is 80% thicker and 30 times stronger than any other blade in the market. The blunt feature of the blade makes it safe and easy to clean. It literally brings cutting edge technology to the kitchen.

MISSION, VISION AND VALUES

Mission Statement

To provide superior blending machine

Vision

"Our vision is to really improve lives,"

Values

Experience, Integrity and Trust

At its core, **Blendtec** is innovation. With greatest satisfaction coming from embracing new ideas, improving upon old ones, and, ultimately, making even better blenders

HISTORY

It all started as nothing serious, with a wedding gift. The top ranged blender known as avocado-hued blender, one of the wedding gift got burnt not too long after his wedding so a thought came into his head that someday he will make a blender that will stand the test of time, 'Someday I will perfect the art of blending and make an indestructible blender', Tom said.

In July 2013, Blendtec won the 2013 Gold Innovation Award for innovations delivered by Blendtec signatures series and other lines of blenders.

In 2017, Blendtec was awarded the 2017 kitchen Innovations Award for its Nitro blending system.

Blendtec is the parent company of the nutrition company BLENDFRESH, which was launched on July 14, 2014

PRODUCTS

Blendtec is in household products and home furnishings.

As a child Tom liked trying the seemingly impossible things. Tom put big engines in little things. In 1975, his curiosity showed up between a vacuum and spilled wheat kernels. His anxious eagerness made him revolutionize home wheat milling industry, moving it away from stone grinding to his patented stainless steel milling heads. He didn't stop at that, he thought of a perfect mixer using freshly milled flour from his mill to make a whole bread in minutes. Afterwards he thought of adding a blender with square rather than the conventional round shaped pitcher.

As Tom grew his mill and mixer business, new ideas developed and he enhanced the blender and began developing commercial blending machines just as the smoothie era began. Today, Tom is still inventing and Blendtec is still growing! All around the world people use Blendtec blenders in their homes, restaurants, smoothie shops, coffee shops, and more. We continue to keep dreaming of new and better ways to build machines that improve the lives of others. It all began with one man and his curiosity. He has shared that vision with others, and with his team, the dream continues to unfold. www.blendtec.com

Generally people both young and old love destruction and so that was the catch that was used and the last video they recorded blended iPhone 6 and within just 2 weeks, the company recorded 2.4 million views.

Ordinarily it takes 38 seconds to blend Frappuccino but with Blendtec product it can be done in 13 seconds and people love prompt delivery.

Creativity/innovation was the key success key that took the company to the peak and it overtook its competitors eg there's a provision on the blender that can be used to make hot soup just press the soup button after adding the ingredients, it can reach more than 110 degrees in few seconds. AMAZING!

1.1 THE ASTONISHING TALES OF A CAPTIVATING MARKETING STRATEGY OF BLENDTEC BLENDER-----‘Will It Blend?’

Will It Blend? Is a marketing video strategy used by Blendtec to showcase its line of blenders especially the powerful total blender which attracted huge views on YouTube channel as well subscribers just within 6 days of the launch. It showed Tom Dickson, the founder, in several attempts to blend various unusual items in order to display how powerful the blender is.

Such as;

“Will it blend? iPhone X” <https://youtu.be/KWqw5SpITg8>

“Will it blend? iPad” <https://youtu.be/1A128d6tbko>

“Will it blend? Ford Fiesta” <https://youtu.be/xRAz6fkr5RQ>

“Will It Blend? Thunder Snaps” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wVlpJVUALSc>

Blendtec launched its first YouTube video about “Will It Blend? In 2006 and since then has had increased market share till date.

Dealing With Low Brand Awareness and Knowledge Problem

It was the quest to build the brand awareness which was the major problem of a small company that had a very powerful solution proven product but no much sales because consumers were not aware of it. As Tom Dickson said, *“even though we had the best blender in the world, people didn’t know who we are. We wanted to demonstrate the power and durability of Blendtec blender.* Online blogs, reviews and discussions showed a gap which suggested that consumers were not willing to buy Blendtec products just because of low brand awareness and knowledge(no advertisements, limited distribution and non-availability of information) and so they were hesitant to make purchases.

Goal

Just with a budget of \$50 a great phenomenon was born. The company had the zeal to revive its brand and create an irresistible mind blowing awareness for its target customers bearing in mind that the company's product is one of the most uninteresting and saturated product in any given departmental store with the challenge of the psychological mindset of consumers that all blenders are the same and so they hardly recall the brand they even use in their kitchen so it appeared to be a hard nut to crack. Blendtec faced with a challenge of creating something of the world that is captivating in order to differentiate its products and a strategy that will increase its brand awareness and consequently market share.

What Blendtec did

It created series of online video known as viral marketing which had low cost in order to increase sales. The company's vice president of sales and marketing, George wright created a marketing campaign video known as "Will It Blend" which featured largely on YouTube. This was after he witnessed Tom Dickson feeding 2x2 wooden board into commercial Blendtec blender in a bid to test how strong and powerful it is and George found it fascinating and thought about how the public will view such an interesting destructive test and that was how the idea of "Will It Blend" was born. They spent \$50 on domain, labcoat, and pair of safety glasses, a bag of marbles, 12 pack of diet coke, aMcDonaldmeal, a rotisserie chicken and a garden rake. Then they asked the CEO, Tom Dickson to blend each of the items they purchased while recording the show on video.

HOW THE IDEA DID CAME ABOUT?

Dickson puts it in the blender and asked a question," **Will It Blend? That is the question**". While it was blending he puts up a reality smile as he waits for the process to end. As soon as it did, he emptied the container on a surface and said, "**Yes It Blends**" They started using one of the hottest marketing strategy on the internet which is the viral video ads. They made series of online YouTube videos titled, Will It Blend? It had a lot of infomercials that showcased their range of products and what they can blend in reality.

According to research by the Kelsey Group, almost half of internet viewers went ahead to visit the company's website and not less than 15% of them purchased the product.

"Will It Blend? Videos turned out to be the 33rd most viewed videos on YouTube and drove the company's **\$399 expensive blender up to 500% in 2008**. He continued with this strategy and was able to video a lot more videos that show cased the blending of a video camera and went ahead to video an idea of returning the blended substance to the store for a price. It attracted so much audience on the internet that got 210,000 people to log in on eBay to view the blended iPad and iPhone. The dust of these items fetched \$800 and \$901 respectively. They quadrupled the vale and donated it to charity (children hospital in Utah)

By 2018, He has recorded 183 series of "Will It Blend? Video which has recorded over **280million views and over 871,000 subscribers** as shown in fig 2.1 and fig 2.11

Blendtec introduced its retail line in stores such as Costco, Sam's Club, and Bed, Bath & Beyond, taking on competitors such as KitchenAid and Vitamix. This was launched in 2006

1.2 EVALUATING THE SUCCESS OF THE 'WILL IT BLEND' SERIES

The success of this marketing strategy is very glaring. This unique innovation gave Blendtec brand a face which would not have been possible coming from a small company that has no budget for advert but needed to increase sales by bringing up its brand. It made it very easy for the brand to be identified by the public. The idea of blending household items was novel just by watching the video, it shows it rather than tell it and visual presentation has been proven over time to attract attention. By watching the video, you can imagine the unimaginable things you would like to blend which seemed impossible but the video shows the possibility with ease.

The clear demonstration of the success is the views on its series of video and the increase in sale till date e.g. is as shown below;

“Will it blend? – Skeleton”<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AsTZm7QtY84>3,523,547 views
•Oct 20, 2011

“Will It Blend? - Super Glue”<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ybzFhk2wRxs>3,138,192 views
•Sep 28, 2011

“Will It Blend? - Diamonds...as far as you know”
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pnonj_84Ju47,992,893 views , Feb 6, 2007

“Will It Blend? - Silly Putty” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jTcIgu1o6N04>4,270,792 views
•Sep 2, 2009

“Will it blend? iPhone 5s and 5c” <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GAuhUTzNwiY>
4,552,567 views, Oct 2, 2013

“Will it blend? Nokia 3310”<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8Sbizs-qAwY>3,493,077 views
•Nov 27, 2012

“Will It Blend? – Crowbar”<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ifzdez7FRbk>
7,819,263 views•Dec 5, 2006

Will It Blend? – iPhone<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qg1ckCkm8YI>
12,784,274 views•Jul 10, 2007

“Will It Blend? – iPad”<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IAI28d6tbko&t=1s>
19,034,072 views, Apr 5, 2010

Blendtec adopted video marketing quite early and made huge success out of it. Ordinarily on the average a business posts 18 videos a month or 216 a year but Blendtec has 183 videos that shows up in their 12 year history. The videos show simplicity and authenticity.

BLENDTEC BEFORE THE INTRODUCTION OF THE VIRAL MARKETING CAMPAIGN, ‘Will It Blend?’

Blendtec’s marketing director, Jeff Robe, says Web popularity has created “a brand presence that we did not have”. Before October 2006, Blendtec spent so long trying to sell their brand to the commercial market (restaurant, stores etc.) but recorded no success with mainstream consumers until the introduction of the **‘Will It Blend?’** Campaign which brought the brand to limelight and gave it huge sales revenue that the company has to deal with being able to meet the demands of their customers.

Undoubtedly, all these have made the Total Blender become a huge success on online sales, specialty shops etc. It has be a known brand all over the world irrespective of its high price tag.

Blendtec celebrates 10 years of success in viral marketing of **“Will It Blend?”** An internet marketing symbol.

Being the most respected and valued blender brand in the world, Blendtec has proven that experience, expertise, focus and daring are the basis for success.

The ultimate desire of a consumer is to have a blender rugged enough to withstand any form of pressure with speed, Blendtec has been called the world’s most advanced blender with the high technology of manufacturing a blender introduced simplicity and effectiveness to the brand. With just a budget of \$50, Will It Blend marketing campaign started and grew into an internationally known brand.

The Success Story.....

1. Sales revenue increased by over 700% since the launching of the campaign.
2. The company’s website has received an unprecedented traffic flow of over 280m views and over 871,000 subscribers representing over 1000% increase in traffic on their website and 10 fold increase in online sales.
3. Till date, their videos have received over 280 million views by unique users and Blendtec has made over \$250 million US dollars in sales.
4. One day after the first video was released on Blendtec website, it received 23,000 hits. After it was released on YouTube, the campaign exploded with their golf ball smoothie that received over 1.7 million views and about half of the viewers went on to make purchases.

Will it Blend’s YouTube Success

Known as one of the most **successful** internet marketing campaigns in history, “**Will It Blend?**” gathered six million views in the first six days.

Example of the success of the “**Will It Blend?**” marketing strategy

Total Youtube viewers	Will it Blend series viewers	Year
705,928 views •Feb 13, 2018	“Will it blend? iPhone X” https://youtu.be/KWqw5SpITg8	2010
19,032,655 views •Apr 5, 2010	“Will it blend? iPad” https://youtu.be/1A128d6tbko	2007
4,848,313 views •Aug 10, 2009	“Will it blend? Ford Fiesta” https://youtu.be/xRAz6fkr5RQ	2018

Table 1.0

Will It Blend? Has got over one million subscribers and over 50 million views.

Blendtec generates \$56m in revenue and has raised \$0 in funding so they have financed their business 100%

Blendtec's Will It Blend? Youtube Statistics

Subscribers Evolution Chart

Views/Videos Evolution Chart

Showing recent 15 entries.

Date		Subscribers		Views	Views	Videos
2020-08-09	Sun	868,000	-	289,912,970	+22,353	183
2020-08-04	Tue	868,000	-1,000	289,890,617	+80,077	183
2020-07-18	Sat	869,000	-	289,810,540	+112,094	183
2020-06-25	Thu	869,000	-1,000	289,698,446	+77,196	183
Date		Subscribers		Views		Videos

2020-06-09	Tue	870,000	-	289,621,250	+22,813	183	-
2020-06-05	Fri	870,000	-	289,598,437	+15,797	183	-
2020-06-02	Tue	870,000	-	289,582,640	+35,724	183	-
2020-05-26	Tue	870,000	-	289,546,916	+16,885	183	-
2020-05-23	Sat	870,000	-	289,530,031	+11,617	183	-
2020-05-21	Thu	870,000	-1,000	289,518,414	+10,852	183	-
2020-05-19	Tue	871,000	-	289,507,562	+11,601	183	-
2020-05-17	Sun	871,000	-	289,495,961	-	183	-
Total Summary		-3,000		+417,009		-	

VIDEOS STAT CHARTS

To date (November 2019) the YouTube channel has had 288, 862, 388 views across all videos and 877,000 subscribers.

Today, Tom is still inventing and Blendtec is still growing! All around the world people use Blendtec blenders in their homes, restaurants, smoothie shops, coffee shops, and more. We continue to keep dreaming of new and better ways to build machines that improve the lives of others. It all began with one man and his curiosity. He has shared that vision with others, and with his team, the dream continues to unfold. www.blendtec.com

1.3 THE ROLE OF CREATIVE MARKETING IN BLENDTEC BLENDER

The soul of branding and advertising is Creativity. It is described as what gives life to the message about the product and services which would have ordinarily been boring or irrelevant in the mind of target audience/customers.

Taking up content marketing is always authentic and real. It's very attractive and persuasive. It makes marketed product acceptable. Creativity that show cases the content of the product has the tendency of attracting the targeted audience.

Developing the content demonstration should be done with high creativity that will loudly announce the brand without any form of ambiguity.

Thinking about innovation/creativity, George Wright of Blendtec comes to mind given the creativity he put around the Blendtec product that gave rise to the much-desired product using viral marketing of series of video of "Will It Blend? Coming up with the creative idea of posting the video of testing process of the Blendtec blender when they were not able to penetrate the market.

Blendtec would have created videos that will show case the blending of fruits to make juice or smoothies but creativity made them come up with over the top approach that created huge traffic on their website.

Blendtec took advantage of the video posts success to partner with other brands without compromising the substance that made his brand strong.

The "Will It Blend" series turned out viral hits for nine years by showcasing their product in a unique but creative way which entertained millions of internet users in a 2 minute video. This is one of the roles of creative marketing with astonishing content marketing.

THE ROLE OF CREATIVE MARKETING IN BLENDTEC "WILL IT BLEND?"

Creative Strategy: An acceptable creative concept formulated before the ad which will carry the theme of the marketing campaign that will serve as the foundation for the message you want to send out to the target customers. Blendtec used an informative and persuasive viral marketing that attracted huge number of views of over 280 million as well over 871,000 subscribers. Here are the roles of creativity in Blendtec "Will It Blend?"

1. **Brand simplicity:** The introduction of the brand by Tom Dickson who appears to be humorous made it easy for people to relate to it.
2. **Usefulness of the brand:** The series of videos are fun to watch and brings to mind the things you wouldn't rather blend.
3. **Reality of the Product:** The reality of the video brings about a spontaneous need to own one even if you have a blender but not one with such features.
4. **Visibility of the brand:** The series of video are made to fit into all Blendtec's marketing efforts.
5. **Customer satisfaction goal:** Consideration about customer satisfaction by Blendtec whenever he puts a question "what do you want me to blend" shows care and concern about customers' needs and provision of solution.
6. **Inevitable nature of the product:** Great blender that works with such show of durability and high performance makes customers not bother about the price tag but just to own one.
7. **Product simplicity of operation:** It shows simplicity in operation which is perceived as work load ease off.
8. **Worth of the product:** It shows the worth of the product which sufficiently defends the cost of the product \$399 and so people purchase without considering the cost having seen the what it can do.

9. **Increase in sales volume:** It significantly increased the sales volume because of how it was made to be perceived by customers.
10. **Household brand:** it created a far reaching house hold name which most consumers would rather have.
11. **Industry leader:** It made it become the leader in the market overtaking the known competitors like Vitamix.
12. **Differentiation from other competitors:** It clearly show cased the difference in durability and power.
13. **Integrity:** With the creativity of the founded being the demonstrator did not hide the company, it rather put a face behind the brand which automatically brings about integrity which is key in gaining customers trust.
14. **Niche:** The style with which the blender was presented carves a niche for the company, the question, **“Will It Blend? That’s the Question”** brings about curiosity and makes the brand stand out

Creativity gives meaning to brand in so many ways like Blendtec “Will It Blend? That’s the Question”

1. **“Will It Blend? That’s the Question** “puts up an attribute of human to the company. The CEO, Tom Dickson getting personally involved gives the company a human face.
2. It’s fun approach appeals to all even children
3. The reality around the brand makes the brand stick to the audience memory e.g. using real items like golf balls, iPhone, iPod, iPad, a lot of things you ordinarily can’t imagine blending that’s the reason why Blendtec sold the blended iPod and blended iPhone on eBay for \$800 and \$901 respectively because people wanted to feel the dust, the post alone attracted 23,000 hits on their website. Power of creative marketing.
4. The creativity idea of being able to suggest things for Dickson to blend and he does it, makes it interactive. Customers can feel them on Facebook, twitter etc not just fake marketing.
5. The campaign is infused into all Blendtec marketing which gives the branding face and brings about trust by the audience.
6. Creativity around the brand makes the expensive price tag not really expensive but worth it and so customers don’t bother about the price but the reality of the demonstrated power of the blender and would rather have one to feel it also in their kitchen or stores.
7. The creativity of if marketing doesn’t sell, it won’t blend took up the sales revenue to more than 700% since the campaign was launched.

2. Establish the role of marketing models with regard to the given organisation; you should include at least one model among (Porter's Model, SWOT Analysis, and PESTLE) and at least one Model among (BCG Matrix, Ansoff Matrix and Product Life Cycle Model). [15 Marks]

2.0 THE ROLE OF MARKETING MODELS TO BLENDTEC

Marketing models were formed to make assumptions about the representation of some variables that describe relationships of interest about a product or service. Marketing models provide basis for solution to marketing problems. They propose viable options of inquiry and information gaps that affects the products/services sale. These are achieved by providing descriptive role. There are various marketing models among which are *Porter's Model, SWOT Analysis, and PESTLE) and at least one Model among (BCG Matrix, Ansoff Matrix and Product Life Cycle Model).*

For the purposes of this assignment for this case study, I shall dwell on

2.1 PORTERS MODEL

Competitors to Blendtec abound but its YouTube marketing method is quite extensive with swerving YouTube viewership growth rate of over **280 million** thus expressing a stable and continuous interest in the show. Will it blend series has an IMDB rating of 7.5/10 and 96% of viewers liking the show.

The concept of showcasing the power of Blendtec's blenders on materials that are not conventional kitchen materials is a brilliant and innovative way of marketing. With the viewers input of suggesting new materials to blend in future episodes, there is a consumer attachment to the program (pseudo advertisement). It raises awareness to new customers about the quality of Blendtec's blenders and its ability to blend a wide range of products. Due to the proliferation of poor-quality blenders, showing the power of their blenders sets it apart from others. In other words, it is a physical proof of its strength and multiplicity of use. 'Evidential' marketing appears convincing to a consumer than a few fluttering words of which the consumers still need a firsthand co-consumer experience to gain assurance. Most consumers are known to get advice from co-consumers or store keepers before purchasing a product. But in the case of the store-keeper it is in a case of choosing between alternatives.

Threat of New Entrants/Potential Competitors: High Pressure

Entry barriers are relatively high in this kind of industry as it requires expertise. There is high cost of switching. There a lot of brands in the market before the introduction of Blendtec powerful and durable blender and so there's fear of unknown for new entrants because of being able to compete with brands like Blendtec. Blendtec is seen not only as a blender but a Brand that has proven its worth and have been able to push up itself to becoming a market leader.

Threat of Substitute Product: Low pressure

There are various kinds of blender in the market even before Blendtec blender was made known and a good brand built, yet it became so successful that it gave rise to a lot of shake offs and now it has become a household name among domestic and industrial consumers and haven proven its worth, it has gained the confidence of their subscribers and so the threat to substitute is very low because of high cost of switching products in this industry. Blendtec blenders are multipurpose to serve virtually every need of industrial and home users.

Bargaining Power Buyer: Low pressure

The customers have low pressure on Blendtec blender because of how expensive it is. Commercial buyers like Starbucks etc have high purchasing power because of the brand they represent and so they don't mind spending any amount to get powerful and durable blender that will serve its premium customers. Individual buyers even though its expensive don't mind buying it because of its necessity in the house and would rather have a good replacement over the ones they were using that were not durable and so will always require replacement almost every 3 months which ultimately will cost much more and their developed trust resulted to loyalty to the product and therefore low bargaining power.

Bargaining Power Supplier: Medium to High Pressure

Blendtec products are proudly made in America. Its parts are not readily seen everywhere and so given the increased demand, it means increase in supplies of spare parts and this will obviously put pressure on supplies. Their bargaining power will be medium to high.

Rivalry Among Existing Competitors: High Pressure

Presently their main competitor is Vitamix among other competitors. The market is saturated with all kinds of blender and that puts high pressure on Blendtec in order to remain the market leader.

Blendtec is faced constantly with competition especially from Vitamix, other less known Chinese companies and home electronics companies worldwide such as Binatone. Competitors are many, but none are ranked as high in terms of blenders' strength, marketing thus becomes easier and it's a known fact that there is no dedicated brand of blender for consumers so it made it easier for Blendtec to grab the market that was waiting to be explored with such a captivating YouTube advert.

2.2 PRODUCT LIFE CYCLE

What Is a Product Life Cycle?

The term product life cycle refers to the length of time a product is introduced to consumers into the market until it's removed from the shelves. The life cycle of a product is divided into 4 stages; introduction, growth, maturity and decline. This idea is used by professionals in the field of marketing and management to ascertain the appropriate time to reduce prices, increase advert, expand to new markets or avenues or rebrand. The process of planning for better ways to continuously remain in business by supporting and maintaining the relevance of the product is known as **Product life cycle management**. A product life cycle is the amount of time a product goes from being introduced into the market until it's taken off the shelves.

When a product is introduced successfully into the market, it increases demand as well as its popularity. The new products in most times push out the old ones thereby replacing them. Companies tend to increase their marketing effort as new ones are introduced.

While a new product needs to be explained, a mature one needs to be differentiated.

The stage of a product's life cycle impacts the way in which it is marketed to consumers. A new product needs to be explained while an old one need to be differentiated from its competitors.

According to Expert Commentator (2018), the Product Life-cycle (PLC) describes the stages of a product from launch to being discontinued. It is a strategy tool that helps companies plan for new product development and refine existing products.

Introduction

Introducing a new product where it's unknown and products are small. The price is often higher as distribution is limited and promotion is personalized, Prior to gaining entrance into the market. Blenders were every kitchen utility, but its introduction of industrial blenders and dried whole fruits are new products that needed an introduction into the market. In the 1870's blenders for commercial purposes were not similar to home blenders. But a difference was made by Blendtec in 1996 when Blendtec developed a unique design that blended industrial materials such as grains. It was so effective that Vitamix (a long-standing competition that existed in the market before Blendtec) decided to use the design in their blenders and thus infringed on media propriety rights. Vitamix lost \$24 million on the lawsuit with Blendtec over design propriety in 2010. Blendtec however used only \$50 to make the difference and became the market leader.

Growth

At this stage consumers have bought the idea about the product and it has started reflecting with the increase in sales volume. Blendtec hit this stage as soon as they introduced the product through viral marketing, **“Will It Blend?”** which exploded sales.

Popularity for the product grown, meaning it is being bought in greater numbers and, with volume, the price declines. Distribution increases and promotion focuses on product benefits. The **“Will It Blend?”** series grew its sales by over 700%. With over 280 million views on YouTube and over 871,000 subscribers.

Maturity

The product competes with alternatives and its pricing drops. Distribution becomes intense (it's available everywhere) and promotion focuses on the differences to competitors' products and that's why Blendtec has over 183 videos with mind blowing items to be blended which keeps attracting audience and buyers to them till date. The less successful products drop at this stage but Blendtec has recorded huge successful and has to deal with meeting up with demand even as at date so their growth stage is still subsisting. Blendtec has embarked on influencers in blogging, instagrammers, etc in order to keep managing their growth and so its still far from getting to maturity stage as the founder and other management executive are still hot on the go for creativity with the outcome of the one they used in introducing the product after it failed with conventional marketing.

Decline

Reaching the end of its life, the product faces fewer competitors. The price may rise and distribution has become selective as some distributors have dropped the product. Promotion aims to remind customers of its existence. In the case of Blendtec is still remains on top because of their brand management strategy which creativity wrapped around it as it sees 50% increase in e-commerce sales.

An example of a product life cycle is typewriter

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